

Voices of Climate Adaptation

A citizen engagement journey
into local climate adaptation
pathways across Europe.

 **Funded by the
European Union**

 cmcc

Voices of Climate Adaptation collects the results of **Adaptation AGORA**, a HORIZON Europe project, which supports the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.

At the heart of the project are collaboration and community engagement. Citizens, civil society organizations, academics, experts, policymakers, and other stakeholders are involved in different geographies to co-design strategies to deal with local impacts of climate change. In this way the project delivers context-specific solutions, recognizing that there is no “one size fits all” in adaptation.

Who we are

The Voices of Climate Adaptation website has been created by **CMCC** within the Adaptation AGORA project.

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Greenish phytoplankton around Gotland, Sweden @USGS

Themes

These themes offer a lens into the journey of adaptation that local communities and citizens are undertaking together to face the impacts of climate change. More than just a response, adaptation becomes an opportunity for collective growth, where science, policy, awareness, and active citizenship come together to shape resilient, empowered communities.

Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

Science and Data

Public Awareness

Policy in the making

CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

Communities lead local adaptation through participation and co-design

Local adaptation requires communities to understand their **specific risks and vulnerabilities**, and design **tailor-made solutions** suited to their social and geographical context.

Citizen participation is key to making adaptation democratic and effective, fostering **behavioral change**, and creating feedback loops between people and institutions.

Engagement helps surface **critical issues**, influence **decision-makers**, and direct **resources** where they are most needed.

Capacity building is essential — equipping individuals and institutions with knowledge, tools, and networks for sustained action.

SCIENCE AND DATA

Robust evidence and contextual data underpin resilient adaptation

Science provides the **knowledge base** needed for effective action, enabling local actors to make **informed decisions** grounded in evidence rather than assumptions.

Continuous data collection and monitoring help identify trends, vulnerabilities, and opportunities for adaptation.

Collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and citizens ensures that science remains contextual and actionable.

Digital platforms and open data **democratize access** to knowledge and enhance **transparency and accessibility** in decision-making.

CLIMATE ADAPTATION as collective growth

Together, these four themes show adaptation as a shared, dynamic process that shapes resilient and empowered communities.

PUBLIC AWARENESS

Awareness builds the foundation for informed action and collective responsibility

Raising awareness means helping people recognize **risks, causes, and urgency** of the climate crisis.

Awareness empowers both **communities and local authorities** to adapt and respond effectively.

Communication must be **clear, relatable, and engaging**, making use of storytelling and local examples.

Combating misinformation is a critical step toward building trust and mobilizing action.

Continuous education and peer learning equip communities with the skills needed to navigate changing climate risks, fostering shared knowledge, mutual support, and collective resilience.

POLICY IN THE MAKING

Adaptive governance ensures fairness and long-term resilience

Climate policies transform ideas and research into tangible **laws, plans, and funding**.

Good policy ensures a **just transition**, protecting vulnerable communities and reducing inequalities.

Policymaking is influenced by **many forces**: science, economy, public opinion, and politics.

Inclusive policy processes should involve citizens, stakeholders, and local actors in **co-design and implementation**.

Current challenges concern uneven participation, limited resources, and processes that do not fully include all community groups.

Local Climate Adaptation and Citizen Engagement

Charles Darwin considered adaptability the most important skill. “It is not the strongest of the species that survives, nor the most intelligent that survives. It is the one that is most adaptable to change,” he said.

Adaptation, a local and community affair

Adaptability has been integral to life on Earth since the beginning. Throughout Earth’s history, species have evolved and adapted to better survive their environment. In the short-term, we can see animals migrating to warmer climates in order to adapt to the changing seasons. Humanity must have the same spirit when it comes to dealing with the impacts of a changing climate, and adaptation plays a key and specific role in this.

Usually, climate change is talked about on a large-scale, with rising sea temperatures, extreme weather events, and melting ice caps. And while **climate change is indeed a global issue, its impacts can be felt at the most local levels**. Different regions experience different climate risks: some may face worsening floods while others experience crippling droughts. **This calls for diverse solutions that are tailored to the geographical, cultural, and social aspects** of local communities. This important **local feature of climate chan-**

ge reflects adaptation. Adaptation solutions can be tailor-made towards the different needs and vulnerabilities of a community. Adaptation, in human systems, is the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects, in order to moderate harm or exploit beneficial opportunities ([IPCC – AR6 glossary](#)). For climate change, it can mean using hard adaptation measures, like building stronger storm defenses, rethinking how we use our land, or redesigning infrastructure. Soft adaptation initiatives focus on non-structural solutions, like utilizing native plants, implementing water management strategies, and using early warning systems. Adaptation is learning to live in a different way, in a different world, constantly adjusting to new challenges.

Adaptation has a lot to do with local needs and resources, with **territorial sustainable development plans, community thinking and collective action**. Each locality and com-

munity has a set of specific needs and vulnerabilities when it comes to tackling climate change impacts. As such, adaptation has an intrinsic local component.

This is why **citizen engagement within adaptation is so important**. Applying adaptation solutions is about understanding how a community can change the way they live in their city, town or rural areas; the way they use information; the way they care for each segment of society, with a wide and inclusive approach. Understanding local climate impacts and barriers to climate adaptation can help with the ability of adaptation solutions to create meaningful impact.

Proper engagement within adaptation creates truly transformative climate adaptation and creates a feedback loop that promotes behavioral change. As engagement within climate adaptation goes up, climate solutions

become more effective and promote adaptation behaviours in citizens, which causes increased support for local, community-led adaptation. While engagement in adaptation is vital, many adaptation initiatives do not address critical issues within communities. **Citizen engagement in climate adaptation can help bring critical issues to light and influence decision-makers and policies** to address them within adaptation solutions. Citizen engagement is not only a democratic way to participate in decision making, but also a way to **make decisions more effectively** and direct the resources in a tailored way. To build meaningful citizen engagement, it is important to have clearly stated engagement objectives, involve a wide range of citizens, and tailor communication towards the specific audience involved. (D1.2)

Along with citizen engagement, capacity building is also an important feature of adaptation. It is defined as “the process by which individuals or organizations obtain, improve, or retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, or other resources to do their work competently” (Climate-ADAPT). Simply put, capacity building improves the ability of a person or organization to complete their objectives. In climate adaptation, capacity building initiatives can help build risk assessment and resilience, empower communities and support social justice, and foster collaboration and knowledge exchange that further strengthen adaptation solutions.

Raising awareness on climate change and adaptation solutions is key. However, the spread of climate disinformation can hinder this. Disinformation can distort the public’s perception of climate change and its risks, can delay action, and affect people’s trust in science and the policy process. Engaging people in ways that respect their communication preferences can promote more knowledge uptake,

and supporting local voices and organizations can help provide respected, trusted, and accurate knowledge that is locally relevant.

Meaningful adaptation is not possible without public understanding and public awareness cannot flourish if it is clouded by disinformation. This is why engagement and capacity building go hand in hand when building climate adaptation initiatives, and why it is a major aspect of the Adaptation AGORA Project.

Climate change can feel like a complex and impossible problem, but adaptation provides us with solutions to not only live with the effects of climate change, but lessen these impacts as well.

A holistic approach to adaptation

Addressing the complex challenge of climate adaptation demands more than just technical solutions, it requires bridging disciplines and integrating diverse forms of knowledge. While climate science provides essential insights into environmental risks and future scenarios, it’s social science that helps us understand how those risks are experienced, perceived, and managed by people and communities. Adaptation measures don’t exist in a vacuum. They unfold in real-world contexts shaped by social norms, economic inequality, political systems, cultural values, and individual behaviors. If we ignore these factors, we risk creating maladaptation, when well-intentioned solutions unintentionally increase vulnerability or create new risks. For instance, installing green infrastructure without ensuring equitable access can widen social gaps rather than reduce them. Social science helps us ask the right

questions: Who benefits from this solution? Who is left out? What power dynamics are at play? How do we build trust and legitimacy in climate decision-making? These questions are critical for designing adaptation strategies that are not only effective on paper but also practical, inclusive, and just in practice. Moreover, integrating community knowledge, lived experience, and local values alongside scientific data fosters stronger public engagement and ownership, which are essential for long-term resilience. **Interdisciplinary collaboration**, between engineers, climate scientists, urban planners, sociologists, and community organizers, transforms adaptation from a technical fix into a **collective process of social transformation**. Climate adaptation is not just about adjusting to impacts, it’s about **reshaping how we live together in a changing world**.

A EU Mission to support local adaptation

The [EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change](#) focuses on supporting EU regions, cities and local authorities in their efforts to build resilience against the impacts of climate change. The Mission was born to complement climate mitigation and address the unavoidable effects of a warmer climate and to drive local communities to be better prepared to cope with those effects. The Mission aims to accompany at least 150 communities to climate resilience, through understanding climate risks, developing pathways for preparation, and implementing innovative solutions by 2030.

The EU regions and cities play a key role in the Mission, as the frontrunners finding and experimenting innovative solutions to local challenges and needs. Regional and local authorities that share the ambitions of the Mission can sign the Mission Charter to join. By doing so, they express their willingness to cooperate, mobilise resources and develop activities in their respective areas and communities to reach their adaptation goals. The number of signatories of the Chart already overcame 300 regional and local authorities.

The Mission funds various projects that focus on adaptation, **like the Adaptation AGORA Project**. Efforts from the EU Mission on Adaptation have produced a wide variety of adaptation tools and resources that address various aspects of climate adaptation, like capacity building, citizen engagement, and case studies that highlight successful adaptation solutions. For example, the [Regional Adaptation Support Tool \(RAST\)](#) supports local and regional authorities with climate adaptation strategies. The tool guides users through the adaptation process, starting with development and ending with monitoring and evaluation. Within the Adaptation AGORA Project, the RAST tool was used in various adaptation and engagement activities (D5.1). Along with the RAST Tool, the EU Mission also provides [do-it-yourself \(DIY\) manuals](#) for citizen engagement that explain what participation tools to use with each of the RAST Tool steps.

The EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change represents one of the many inter-regional efforts in Europe to address the climate crisis.

Citizens do care about climate challenges

Climate change remains among the top three concerns of Europeans. An overwhelming majority support action across the EU to tackle the climate crisis and make Europe the first climate-neutral continent, according to the [latest Eurobarometer survey](#) by the European Commission.

Among the main results of the survey:

- European citizens identify climate change as the third most serious problem facing the world after poverty, hunger and lack of drinking water, and armed conflicts.
- 88% of respondents – and at least 70% in each Member State – agree that greenhouse gas emissions should be reduced to a minimum while offsetting the remaining emissions for a climate-neutral EU economy by 2050.
- More than nine in ten respondents (93%) have taken at least one specific action to fight climate change, most notably by reducing and recycling waste (70%) and cutting down on consumption of disposable items whenever possible (53%).

These data are encouraging and confirm the **importance of involving local communities** in climate action, as they show a high degree of care and commitment to the topic already in place in many European regions. Citizen support of climate solutions helps build community resilience and puts pressure on decision-makers to implement effective and widespread policy.

From knowledge to action, the circle of climate movement

There is great power in individual action, but it can be difficult to know where to start. There are a few key elements to having meaningful and successful climate participation. First, you must have concrete knowledge of your area and what local climate impacts are most affecting your community. You can get informed by making sure you are getting accurate scientific information and data, through your local institutions, climate organizations, or credited climate resources, like the Adaptation AGORA Digital Academies. Being informed sets you up for providing the [most accurate insights](#) into adaptation solutions.

Once you have that knowledge, you can inform others, through volunteering, or even just by having conversations with your family, friends, and community members. Raising awareness among your community can [spark further participation](#). Informing your community also means letting local policy and decision-makers know you're aware and ready to take action. This is one of the best ways to begin change.

After informing your community and local authorities, you can **participate in co-planning adaptation solutions and initiatives**. Co-production means collaborating with researchers, policy and decision-makers, and the public to create comprehensive solutions. This step allows people from all sectors of a community to come together and provide information, insights, and personal knowledge that will create comprehensive adaptation solutions. [Co-production](#) feeds into the next step, decide. All the knowledge and data created during the previous steps helps cre-

ate informed decisions on the most effective adaptation solutions and policy decisions for a community.

[Meaningful climate participation begins with you!](#) Understanding the science and data of your area gives you the resources to build awareness in your community, engage in co-planning, and help build effective adaptation solutions and policies.

Science and Data

“Without data, you’re just another person with an opinion”.
- W. Edwards Deming

From data to decisions

Science and policy are often treated like different worlds, but in order to have effective climate adaptation, it is essential that science and policy work hand in hand. Climate science often refers to critical insights gathered on changing weather patterns, sea level rise, ecosystem disruptions, and vulnerabilities across different sectors, like agriculture, water, health, and infrastructure.

Using climate science and data is essential for **creating effective and comprehensive climate policies that help build resilience, enhance public participation, and foster sustainable development**. Science helps inform policy in two major ways: by providing data-driven insight, and identifying opportunities for adaptation. Policy then takes that scientific information and transforms it into actionable frameworks. Without policy, scientific data would remain in reports instead of being applied in real-world action.

Data-driven policy helps governments and institutions use resources effectively, measure impact, and avoid unnecessary costs. When policy decisions are based on scientific data, it becomes more transparent, accountable, and responsive to the people and communities' needs. The **connection between science**

and policy ensures that **future decisions about adaptation are informed by the best available data**, which helps communities respond to climate risks. Linking science and policy **also helps build public trust**. It shows that the decisions made are guided by what works and turns good intentions into **effective action**.

Despite the importance of science in decision-making, scientific knowledge is not always easily accessible or understandable for policy makers and the general public. Bridging this gap requires **continuous dialogue and mutual understanding**. This is why science-policy interfaces, like the IPCC, are so important. They help translate complex scientific data into concrete actions for communities.

The Adaptation AGORA Project also attempts to bridge this gap, by providing multiple avenues for people, governments, and decision-makers to access easily understandable climate information. To have truly impactful climate adaptation, a key factor is science-policy collaboration. It is how we move from knowing the impacts of climate change to actually doing something about them.

One of the main ways Adaptation AGORA directly addresses the gap between science and policy is through the Digital Academies. In the [Academy on Climate Data Risks & Tools](#), interested users can find accurate and easy to understand climate information on a range of topics, like adaptation, citizen science, and climate justice. The Academies go a step beyond simply providing information. These digital platforms provide a **truly individualized experience**, as you can curate the platform for your personal use. Whether you need to find climate information specific to your area, you want to take modules to grow your climate knowledge, or you want to share climate facts, the Digital Academies provide the space for you to do so. Truly transformative change means collaborating and expanding climate knowledge at all levels, and the Digital Academies take a step towards this goal.

[climate adaptation strategy](#) by engaging with members from various sectors to identify critical vulnerabilities and areas to strengthen resilience.

In Zaragoza, Spain, [project workshops with different local communities](#) helped co-create a vulnerability report that integrated social, economic, and environmental factors.

These efforts help bridge the gap between science and policy, bringing members from both areas together to create strong and comprehensive climate action. The tool Adaptation AGORA has designed to facilitate these interactions is the [Agora Community HUB](#), a digital space within the weADAPT platform that connects stakeholders, scientists, policymakers, media, and citizens to share knowledge and collaborate on climate adaptation. It offers tools, case studies, and experiences that help local governments and communities identify peers, overcome challenges, and learn from ongoing implementation efforts, while fostering networking across regions and initiatives.

Pilot regions insights

In the Pilot regions of Rome (Italy), Dresden (Germany), Zaragoza (Spain), and Malmö (Sweden), the Adaptation AGORA Project has held various workshops, group sessions, and webinars that brought together the general public, city officials, academics, and stakeholders from sectors including urban planning, public health, biodiversity, industry and civil society. These events targeted different groups, like youth, elderly, and vulnerable populations, and collected local knowledge to help inform adaptation solutions for each of the Pilot regions.

The efforts of the Adaptation AGORA Project highlight the importance of community engagement within science and policy. For instance, in the Pilot region of Rome, Italy, Adaptation AGORA helped [co-design the city's](#)

The Agora Community HUB is also a tool that enlarges the community of the project, allowing **followers** to join the discussion and share their experiences. Followers are other regions as well as associations, organizations and institutions that are involved in the process of adaptation to climate change. The followers' concept expands the project's community beyond the pilot areas, engaging more people across Europe. It allows followers to share their specific needs and benefit from the project's insights and results from the pilots, supporting adaptation efforts at a broader scale.

How climate disinformation undermines climate action

It has been well-documented that human activities bear responsibility for the modern-day climate change we are experiencing.

However, a major barrier in bridging the gap between science and policy is the spreading of disinformation.

Disinformation can confuse and mislead the public, creating distrust in science and climate data and ultimately decreasing people's willingness to participate in climate action.

Disinformation greatly threatens climate action. It can [erode public support and trust in climate adaptation authorities and policies](#) that causes division and isolation, and snowballs into a distrust in science. By planting seeds of doubt and flooding people with false claims, disinformation slows down progress and makes it much harder to build support. While [experts clearly show the link between human activity and climate change](#), disinformation campaigns cast doubt over the expert consensus, exaggerate uncertainties, and promote false solutions that delay real action. It is, therefore, essential for accurate and credible climate information to be available to policy-makers and the general public to help fight disinformation and build effective climate adaptation policy and public awareness.

Public Awareness

“Only if we understand, will we care. Only if we care, will we help. Only if we help, shall all be saved”

– Jane Goodall

From awareness to action

Climate change threatens to create a more unstable and dangerous present and future. We can see this through the increasing rate and intensity of storm events and weather extremes. This marks the **importance of climate change awareness**. Public awareness paves the way for managing climate impacts and reducing vulnerabilities. Building public awareness of climate change helps equip local authorities and communities with the knowledge and resources needed to adapt and respond to climate risks. Certain groups can be more vulnerable to the climate crisis than others, making climate change awareness vital for these groups to adapt.

Awareness of climate change can also lead to [changes in behavior and societal support in adaptation measures](#). It helps people understand the causes, impacts, and urgency of climate change. By increasing public awareness, people can recognize how their daily choices, like driving a car instead of taking the bus, can contribute to greenhouse gas emissions. Having successful awareness campaigns, scientific communication, and education initiatives help supply people with accurate information that enable them to make informed decisions, and support adaptation policies and initiatives. As public **awareness grows**,

so does **the sense of shared responsibility and collective action**. Raising public awareness can increase enthusiasm. Climate change requires widespread participation from communities, governments, businesses, and individuals. When people are aware of the impact of climate change, they are more likely to demand stronger climate policies and more sustainable practices.

Capacity building is essential in raising public awareness. It equips people with the **knowledge, resources, and skills** needed to understand climate information and to take action. Capacity building goes farther than just providing information, it helps empower individuals, organizations, local governments, and whole communities to collaborate and build adaptation solutions that are best for their situation. Access to training, tools, and knowledge that make climate information relatable makes people more likely to engage, demand for solutions, and change behaviors. Capacity building also helps in bridging gaps of knowledge, especially for areas where climate impacts are great, but public understanding is limited due to the lack of resources and education. Capacity building is a long-term commitment, but one that **will build climate resilience from the ground up**.

In Adaptation AGORA, capacity building was heavily used throughout engagement activities. Building from other EU projects and from previous project activities, Adaptation AGORA compiled the best capacity building methods for successful engagement and maximized the potential of project events. For instance, storytelling was used throughout project workshops to connect with participants and to relay climate information in a more relatable and easy to understand way.

The capacity building tools, methods, and resources gathered from other projects and from Adaptation AGORA events have been compiled into [various documents and reports](#), to help future projects, organizations, and communities apply capacity building methods to build public awareness and climate action.

Moreover, **all capacity building resources produced under the project are systematized in a [set of one-pagers](#)** which can be consulted as a catalogue. Peer-learning activities are also key to build strong networks and facilitate mutual exchange.

Communication and engagement at the heart of climate solutions

Raising public awareness can take many forms, and as everyone responds differently, using multiple communication styles and engagement strategies is the best way to raise awareness throughout a community. As part of the Adaptation AGORA Project, public communication and engagement is at the core of what we do. Throughout our project, we have held various public engagement events to understand and co-design adaptation initiatives that are tailored to specific communities.

When it comes to raising public awareness of climate change, how we talk about it can be just as important as what we say. Effective communication strategies bridge the gap between science and the general public. If the message is too technical, too negative, or too overwhelming, people may get confused or anxious, leading them to tune out the message altogether. This is why successful communication makes the message relatable, clear, and empowering.

Knowing your audience is one of the best ways to engage with your community. While some respond best to statistical, jargon-heavy facts, others may need information with more layman’s terms. Not everyone connects with melting ice caps and extreme climate scenarios. Understanding your audience means connecting with their daily problems and concerns. Linking local impacts to climate change is a key way of engaging with your audience and connecting them to the climate crisis. **Amplifying trusted voices** can help bring credibility to your message. Local actors in the climate space make your movement reliable, and people are more likely to listen and enga-

ge with someone they relate to. **Storytelling** can also be a power tool. Personal experiences bring reality to climate change and can create empathy among your audience.

Climate communication is not just about talking to your audience, it's about **listening, engaging, and giving communities a role within the solution.** Workshops, town halls, and social media campaigns are great ways to spark conversation about climate change. Continual dialogue builds trust, promotes local knowledge, and fosters collective action.

How to overcome the Disinformation barrier

One of the best ways to fight climate change is to spread information among communities. But what happens when this information gets twisted, reworded, or muffled by inaccurate sources? This is climate disinformation and it is designed to stall climate action. [Climate disinformation is a serious barrier in the climate fight.](#) It causes doubt and distrust in science, weakened support for climate action, and can hinder policy and international action. The [IPCC AR6 report](#) shows that while evidence clearly links human activities to climate change, misguided efforts clouded by disinformation can lead to public polarization, which delays and corrupts climate action.

Now this is not to say you should blindly accept scientific information. Being skeptical is natural and a good thing to practice. It means that you consider all sources of information before coming to a conclusion. However, you'll find that arguments expressing [climate skepticism](#) typically use cherry-picked information or outdated sources to "win" their argument. This is not skepticism, it is ignoring the facts and spreading disinformation. Climate disinformation can take many forms, from hard denial and conspiracy theories to softer attempts at discrediting science, claims that climate change is not man-made or that the threat is not as bad as scientists say. Some will use cherry-picked statistics to try and discredit scientific evidence or misleading headlines to lessen the impact of climate change. Disinformation is often caused by [local actors, like political parties, and mainstream media.](#) This differs from country to country, from community to community. This is where media literacy comes in.

With the rise of social media, disinformation is trickier than ever. It is easy to become

overwhelmed by all the differing information available. It is, therefore, important to be knowledgeable about disinformation and ways to combat it.

The best ways to [recognize climate disinformation](#):

- 1. Check your sources.** If your source references scientific institutions, peer-reviewed journals, and reputable news outlets, then you are good to go!
- 2. Pay attention to the language and tone.** If your source uses sensationalist language, exaggerations, and appeals to strong emotions, then it's best to fact-check it.
- 3. Fact-check.** It is important to make use of independent fact-checking websites available to help you verify claims. In Europe, the [EDMO](#) is a major independent fact-checking organization that provides numerous resources on disinformation and other topics. These disinformation tells are part of the [larger capacity of media literacy.](#) Media literacy encompasses all the technical, cognitive, social, civic, and creative capacities that allow citizens to access, have a critical understanding of the media, and interact with it. Building indi-

vidual and communal media literacy helps people break down disinformation, making them less-likely to be affected by it. Greater public awareness also plays a vital role in fighting disinformation. As communities are more informed about climate change, they will be less likely to succumb to climate disinformation. Growing the capacity of individuals and communities makes the fight against disinformation that much more stronger.

To do our part in the fight against climate disinformation, the [Climate Change Disinformation Academy](#) produced by the Adaptation AGORA Project creates an online safe space for climate information and aims to build the awareness of users with reliable climate change information and fact-checked data from credible sources. The Academy handles topics like media literacy to enhance users ability to identify disinformation and provides real-world examples of climate disinformation. The fight against disinformation is one of the biggest barriers to climate action, and platforms like the Climate Change Disinformation Academy are essential in building comprehensive public awareness.

Policy in the making

“I have learned that the problems of others are the same as my own. Getting out of them all together is politics.”
- Lorenzo Milani

Governing change

Combating climate change hinges on implementing effective policy. It is what turns good ideas and scientific research into laws, plans, and funding. Without strong climate policies in place, efforts to cut emissions or adapt to climate impacts often end up scattered, underfunded, or take too slow to make a real difference. Climate policies provide the structure and direction needed to drive meaningful, long-term change at the local, national, and global levels.

Good climate policy helps make the transition to more sustainable practices fair. Not everyone contributes to climate change equally and not everyone has access to the same resources to adapt. Smart policy can protect vulnerable communities, can ensure workers in high-emission industries aren't left behind, and hold big polluters accountable.

One policy, many influences

Climate policy is one of the best ways to combat climate change, as it is the primary way governments and institutions respond to climate risks. It includes the rules, strategies, and incentives that guide everything, from cutting emissions to protecting communities from climate disasters.

Climate policy is shaped by a variety of factors, a major one being science. **Science-based policies provide the most informed decisions, but exactly how that scientific information gets turned into action depends on who is in power, what the public is demanding, and who is informing the policymakers.** Many policymakers rely on climate data, research, and expert recommendations to understand the impacts of climate change and what actions are most critical, and organizations like the IPCC and state environmental agencies help set the global agenda. There are other factors that influence policy, like politics. **Who is in office and what their priorities are can influence climate action significantly.** Some governments make major strides and push ambitious green policies, while others delay climate initiatives due to

pressure from powerful industries or because climate action is not politically relevant. While climate change is a long-term issue, politics often has short-term visions.

Economics is another huge factor in climate policy. Job growth, long-term savings, and the creation of new industries can be major advantages for green policies. However, if implementing a green policy seems too expensive or threatens existing jobs, there can be major resistance. This is why many green policymakers push for “**just transitions**” policies, which help workers and communities shift to greener industries. **Corporate influence and lobbying** can also influence climate policy, both in positive and negative instances. Some businesses support climate action, and push for strong, science-based policies. Others, like those tied to fossil fuels industries, may try to delay or weaken climate laws to protect profits.

This highlights the importance of speaking up and why staying informed really matters, as **public opinion can sway leaders to act faster.** When enough people care about the climate movement and demand action, leaders take notice. Protests, petitions, voting, and participating in local climate action can shift the conversation and increase political will. Climate movements led by young people, Indigenous groups, scientists, and everyday citizens have already made a huge impact on shaping climate agendas globally.

Strong climate policy is what separates talk from action. It sets clear goals, creates accountability, and helps make sure climate solutions are fair and effective.

A climate policy, white paper

Community engagement in climate policy is of vital importance to the climate movement. The Adaptation AGORA Project has showcased new ways of immersing citizen engagement into adaptation planning and policy. Across the four Pilot regions, project efforts have demonstrated that **policies are not truly effective until they include local voices.** Project efforts have analyzed policy and stakeholder engagement across the Pilot regions, at the national and EU levels, to gain an understanding of current citizen participation within climate action. Databases, reports, and other resources have been created to reflect our findings, looking at different elements like how many stakeholders are included, what participatory mechanisms are used and in what capacity? Are they private or public? Required or voluntary?

All of this analysis helps us understand the current state of climate policy in Europe and can show where policies are falling short. What we have found is that while current climate policy is very enthusiastic, **there are still gaps**, like a **lack of accessibility and inclusion of vulnerable groups**, and a **shortage of participatory** elements being implemented. Many municipalities were found to have **inadequate human and financial resources** to effectively engage with stakeholders and communities were seen to have a lack of awareness and motivation to participate in climate action.

From our findings, we are able to build **recommendations to create more inclusive adaptation solutions** that foster resilience from the ground up. Gaining and deeper understanding how people are most affected, which communities are most at risk, and which groups are underrepresented helps build comprehensive climate action that will address the needs of the **entire community**.

Within the **Adaptation AGORA project**, a [policy white paper](#) was developed to address the critical gap between high-level ambition and on-the-ground implementation. It argues that, to move from isolated successes to a new standard of climate governance, **Europe must adopt a holistic approach to scaling engagement**.

The white paper presents a **strategic roadmap** based on a comprehensive analysis of current research, policies, and practices. It builds on a synthesis of evidence from academic literature, EU policy instruments, EU-level documents, participatory practices, and empirical insights gathered throughout the Adaptation AGORA project.

Radar image of Catalan coasts in Spain, from Copernicus Sentinel-1 ©ESA

Pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe: Italy, Germany, Sweden, and Spain, come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

These inspiring experiences are the result of Adaptation AGORA's work across diverse regions, engaging local communities and a broader network of over 35 followers. Together, they're tackling place-based climate challenges and co-creating practical, inclusive solutions, designed to foster collaboration, share best practices, and raise awareness.

Italy - The Eternal Resilience

Sweden - Keeping Malmö Cool

Spain - Urban and Rural Adaptation

Germany - Go where Citizens are

Four pilot regions

From the four corners of Europe come powerful stories of climate adaptation, told through the voices of those living it.

Sweden

Keeping Malmö Cool

Nordic life is built for cold — bodies, homes, whole cities. But rising heat is a new, unexpected challenge changing everything. Yet a city's ability for adaptation often rises from hidden corners, places you would never expect to drive such change.

Germany

Go where Citizens are

Citizen engagement is a challenging journey. But in Dresden, it became truly meaningful when we stepped into people's spaces, listened to their voices, and met them where they are, rather than expecting them to come to us.

Spain

Urban and Rural Adaptation

From villages to cities, every voice matters in climate adaptation. In Aragón, climate challenges and solutions from both dimensions bridge countryside and urban settlements, reflecting the full diversity of our society.

Italy

The Eternal Resilience

Rome has endured centuries of history, but today it faces a new trial: the relentless pressures of climate change. Can the eternal city rise once again, this time by turning crisis into opportunity?

Common participatory pathway

Diverse territories converge into one shared approach shaped through dialogue, collaboration, and local experience.

Italy - The Eternal Resilience

Rome has endured centuries of history, but today it faces a new trial: the relentless pressures of climate change. Can the eternal city rise once again, this time by turning crisis into opportunity?

Context

Rome, the Eternal City. A story unlike any other in the world: iconic, unique, steeped in history. For centuries, it has stood resilient in the face of time. But can it rise once again, this time to meet the challenge of climate change? **Can adaptation become a springboard for modernisation** and a chance to **improve the quality of life** for all who live and visit here?

Rome, like many major metropolitan areas, faces mounting climate pressures. **Heatwaves** are no longer the exception but the norm, stretching across **longer summers** and testing the limits of residents and tourists alike. **Managing water**, both when it's scarce and when it's overwhelming, is becoming increasingly complex. From **extreme weather**

events to the **fragile coastal areas**, and from the **protection of a diverse population** to the growing gaps between neighbourhoods, **the challenges are as varied as the city itself**. What affects one area of Rome might not affect another the same way. Some districts are far more vulnerable, and targeted action there is urgent.

But Rome, unlike its beautiful stone memories, is not standing still. The city has embarked on its **climate adaptation journey** with a dedicated local strategy. The first step was gathering solid **scientific input from top research institutes**, including the [CMCC](#), coordinator of the Adaptation AGORA project. From there, the draft strategy was brought to life through a public participation process, supported by workshops and focus groups organized by the project. After hearing directly from the people of Rome, the [adaptation strategy](#) was fine-tuned and officially adopted by the City Assembly in January 2025.

Stakeholders

This pilot case study convened a wide range of stakeholders, including representatives from civil society, academia, the private sector, and non-profit organizations, to address the **challenges outlined in the city's initial adaptation strategy**. The engagement process focused on **ten key areas**, from water management and urban infrastructure to cultural heritage, health, and biodiversity, pinpointing **where Rome is most at risk**. Stakeholders identified the city's main vulnerabilities and needs, while also highlighting ways to engage citizens as crucial partners in shaping a successful adaptation strategy.

The Municipality of Rome

Rome approved its **first Climate Adaptation Strategy in January 2025**, setting priorities, goals, and measures to prepare the city for increasingly frequent and intense climate impacts. This process matched perfectly with the progress of the Adaptation AGORA project, where the **Climate Office** of the Municipality, represented by its **Director, Edoardo Zanchini**, has been the **key partner in the Italian pilot**.

Drafted in January 2024 after extensive research and scientific collaboration, the strategy went through months of **public consultation**, with workshops, local meetings, and citizen input helping shape the final plan. Adaptation AGORA workshops were part of this consultation process. **The strategy focuses on four urgent challenges: heavy rains and floods** threatening neighborhoods and infrastructure, **water shortages** from prolonged droughts, **rising urban heat** with health risks,

and coastal erosion worsened by storms and **sea-level rise**. The strategy outlines concrete adaptation measures, responsibilities, costs, and funding sources, along with a monitoring system and annual updates to keep citizens informed and engaged.

Other public authorities

The engagement process also involved **key public authorities**, including the **State Property Agency (Agenzia del Demanio)** and the **Lazio Regional Health Department (DEP Lazio)**. Their participation brought **crucial perspectives to the discussion tables**, enriching the debate with insights **from their specific areas of responsibility**. The **State Property Agency** highlighted how **climate change directly affects public assets and infrastructure**, raising urgent questions about the resilience of state-owned buildings and the preservation of Italy's vast heritage. Meanwhile, **DEP Lazio shed light on the critical climate-health nexus**, stressing the challenges of managing public health risks in a changing climate. A particular focus was on the growing threat of heatwaves in Rome, a metropolis that must not only safeguard its residents but also protect the millions of visitors it welcomes each year. By sharing their sector-specific expertise, **these stakeholders helped connect climate impacts to tangible, real-world challenges**, from safeguarding cultural and economic assets to ensuring the health and safety of citizens, making them essential partners in shaping a comprehensive adaptation strategy.

Civil Society

Civil society associations played a vital role in the engagement process, bringing fresh energy, **diverse perspectives, and a strong**

sense of community ownership to the discussions. The **youth section of WWF Italy** and the **activists of Fridays for Future** reminded decision-makers of the **urgency of action**, amplifying the **voices of younger generations** who will live with the long-term consequences of climate change. **The Italian Red Cross** contributed **its experience in managing emergencies**, underlining the importance of **preparedness and rapid response in protecting vulnerable populations** during extreme events. Equally important was the **participation of migrant associations** representing Rome's multicultural communities, who emphasized the **need for inclusive strategies** that account for the diverse realities of those living in the city. Together, these groups helped **ensure that the adaptation strategy** was not only scientifically sound and institutionally robust, but also **socially just, inclusive, and rooted in the values of solidarity and collective resilience**.

Academia

Academia also brought a crucial contribution to the engagement process, represented by the **University of Roma Tre**, and in particular its **Faculty of Architecture**. Their **expertise in urban planning** offered valuable insights into **how the city's spaces can be reimagined to withstand climate pressures while remaining livable and inclusive**. Beyond technical solutions, they stressed the **importance of involving citizens** in co-designing adaptation measures, **ensuring that urban transformation is both participatory and responsive to the real needs of communities**. By bridging scientific knowledge with practical urban strategies and citizen engagement, academia reinforced the idea that climate adaptation in Rome must be both evidence-based and deeply rooted in civic participation.

Challenges

In recent years, **Rome has been experiencing an acceleration of climate change impacts, with rising temperatures and shifting rainfall patterns** marked by long periods of **drought followed by sudden, intense downpours**. The city faces **serious hydrogeological risks**: rivers like the Tiber and the Aniene cut through its territory, leaving some neighborhoods highly exposed to flooding during heavy rains. This vulnerability is compounded by past unauthorized construction in areas that were never meant to be urbanized because of their proximity to rivers and flood risks.

Water management is another pressing issue. Rome has historically been blessed with an abundance of high-quality water, a legacy

dating back to the Romans who built aqueducts to channel pristine water from the Apennines. But this long-standing advantage is under threat. Increasing droughts will make securing water supplies a top priority, requiring both investments in infrastructure and new approaches to reduce the use of drinking water, for example, by expanding the reuse of treated water, an area where the city is already investing heavily.

Rome also has **18 kilometers of coastline**, where **rising sea levels** are beginning to take a toll. The challenge is to **assess all these impacts**, across neighborhoods, infrastructures, and landscapes, and to use data, research, and scientific studies **to plan the city's transformation**. The goal is not only to make Rome resilient to climate change, but also to seize the opportunity to make it more modern, livable, and socially just, addressing long-standing inequalities in the process.

The greatest challenge lies at the neighborhood level. Public spaces need to be re-designed to be safer, cooler, and more welcoming, reducing climate risks while improving daily life for both residents and tourists. But Rome is a big and diverse city: depending on the area, temperature differences can reach 5–6°C between densely built-up, asphalt-heavy districts and those near large green areas or on the coast, where heat is naturally mitigated. **These uneven climate impacts overlap with social inequalities,** age, income, and other vulnerabilities, making some communities particularly at risk.

The city’s Adaptation Strategy estimates that **around 9% of Rome’s population is at risk during heatwaves.** Data clearly shows **where action is most urgent:** for instance, in the **eastern districts,** where green spaces are scarce. Here, environmental measures must go hand in hand with social, health, and communication strategies to protect and support the city’s most vulnerable residents.

Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project’s four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a **structured participatory pathway:** an inception workshop to map key stakeholders, engage different target audiences and decision-makers, and identify local barriers and vulnerabilities; followed by focus groups with specific populations to better understand their concerns and unique perspectives; and culminating in a final co-creation workshop

aimed at developing actionable proposals and contributions to adaptation measures. The **emphasis was on soft adaptation measures,** non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure.

In Rome, more **than 100 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, academia, and business were identified and engaged throughout the process. This approach bridged community insights with policymaking, laying the foundation for long-term impact.

2. Inception workshop

November 2023: The process began with an **in-depth stakeholder mapping, identifying 42 key actors** across government, academia, civil society, and the private sector. This wasn’t just about listing names, it was about ensuring diversity, gender balance, and inclusion of underrepresented voices from the start. The first big milestone was the organisation of the **inception workshop, where the 30 participants mapped out vulnerabilities and gaps in Rome’s adaptive capacity,** setting the foundation for collective action. To maximize accessibility, the event was hosted in a venue chosen with public transport challenges in mind, and all materials were designed to be visually clear and easy to understand. Participants were divided into **small, interdisciplinary breakout groups** and guided through structured **discussions on climate vulnerabilities and adaptive capacity gaps across nine critical sectors** in line with the adaptation strategy of the city of Rome, from **water and infrastructure to health and cultural heritage.** Using infographics and color-coded post-its, participants mapped out both sector-specific and cross-cutting issues, while trained facilitators ensured balanced dialo-

gue. The workshop concluded with a **dynamic table-to-table feedback round,** allowing all groups to review and refine each other’s contributions. This marked the **formal launch of the participatory pathway,** anchoring it in both inclusivity and collective ownership.

3. Focus groups

Summer and Autumn 2024: The second step shifted from exploration to dialogue through a series of thematic focus groups. **Workers, youth, multicultural communities, and health professionals.** Each group brought different lived experiences and perspectives, from everyday workplace challenges to youth activism, public health concerns, and traditional knowledge from migrant communities. The sessions combined open dialogue with **structured facilitation techniques** such as Think–Pair–Share, the Nominal Group Techni-

que, and 1–2–4–All. Participants first reflected on vulnerabilities and needs, then worked together to define **priority “soft” adaptation measures,** actions like awareness campaigns, education programs, or community-based early warning systems. A specially developed **Citizen Engagement Card Deck** helped participants evaluate which participatory methods (e.g. mentorship programs, citizen assemblies, peer-learning circles) could best support the implementation of the selected soft adaptation measure. This tool proved particularly effective in making the process accessible, even for participants unfamiliar with formal participatory mechanisms.

4. Co-creation workshop

January 2025: The final step brought the process full circle with the co-creation workshop, which took place in **January 2025, just as the City of Rome officially adopted its first Climate Adaptation Strategy.** The timing underscored how the participatory pathway had actively supported the city throughout the strategy’s development, creating direct links between institutional planning and citizen-driven contributions. A total of **44 participants** came together to transform the priorities identified in earlier phases into concrete adaptation proposals. Working in **six breakout groups supported by facilitators, participants revisited earlier findings on vulnerabilities and adaptive capacity gaps, then refined them into actionable measures.** A dedicated set of visual cards and infographics synthesized the outputs from the focus groups, serving as prompts to guide discussion. Each group was asked to classify proposals into thematic domains such as commu-

nication, education, or both, ensuring clarity and coherence. Alongside these impact-related criteria, **participants also assessed the practical feasibility of each approach**, considering factors such as implementation costs, logistical accessibility, required skills, and the availability of institutional support. Following the group-based assessment, a final plenary discussion provided space for each group to present its insights and recommendations. The integration of tailored facilitation techniques, structured visual tools, and thematically focused prompts across all phases of the process ensured that each session yielded two interrelated outcomes: a shortlist of soft adaptation measures and a corresponding set of preferred engagement strategies to support their implementation.

By the end of the workshop, **participants had produced a set of tangible, socially oriented adaptation actions**, grounded in both scientific evidence and community experience. The workshop thus represented the culmi-

nation of the participatory journey: from mapping and listening to co-designing strategies that complemented and reinforced Rome's newly adopted adaptation strategy, helping to ensure it is not only a technical document, but a living, inclusive, and community-owned pathway toward resilience. For more detailed information on the workshop, you can consult the [dedicated report](#).

Participation was the key topic of a [dedicated webinar of the peer-to-peer learning series](#). Participatory experiences were discussed involving also the Adaptation AGORA's follower Friuli Venezia Giulia Region.

Results

Education and community at the heart of climate adaptation

The engagement process in Rome showed a clear priority: **education and community awareness are the cornerstones of climate adaptation**. Participants agreed that schools, communities, and public spaces should be at the center of change.

A key proposal was to **embed climate education in school curricula**, supported by practical, locally relevant activities like workshops and field trips. This was seen as a long-term investment in future generations, enabling young people to become climate advocates within their families and communities. Beyond schools, participants stressed the **importance of awareness-raising initiatives**, from public events and campaigns to neighborhood consultations. When paired with effective communication, these activities were seen as essential for mobilizing broad participation. Other promising ideas included **collaborative mentoring programs**, to foster bottom-up involvement and ownership of adaptation strategies, and **community skill-building workshops**, especially in schools, offering low-cost, high-impact ways to strengthen local resilience.

Across all discussions, the reasons behind the preferences became clear:

- **Long-term impact:** school programs seen as investments in future generations.
- **Inclusivity and accessibility:** public events and consultations valued for their ability to involve diverse groups.
- **Adaptability:** mentoring and community workshops praised for tailoring solutions to local needs.
- **Feasibility:** preference for approaches that

build on existing infrastructure (schools, public spaces) to minimize costs and maximize reach.

Participants co-created a **final package of “soft” adaptation measures** centred on **education, awareness, and community engagement**. This mix was considered the most effective pathway to strengthen Rome's collective capacity to face climate change, combining the energy of youth, the inclusivity of public events, and the ownership fostered by participatory approaches.

Italy's pathway

Rome

The Eternal Resilience

watch the video

Rome, the Eternal City. For centuries, it has stood resilient in the face of time. But can it rise once again, this time to meet the challenge of climate change? Can adaptation become a springboard for modernisation and a chance to improve the quality of life for all who live and visit here? Unlike its beautiful stone memories, Rome is not standing still, but it has embarked on its climate adaptation journey with a dedicated local strategy.

LOCAL IMPACTS

VULNERABILITIES

- 18 Km of coastline
- 3 rivers: Tiber and its affluents Aniene and Almone
- 5-6 °C temperature rise
- 9% of population at risk

RISKS & CHALLENGES

- Floods
- Heatwaves
- Water management
- Coastal erosion
- Longer summers

More than 100 **STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED**, from 4 key groups.

Municipality

Other public authorities

Civil society

Academia

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

RESULTS

EDUCATION

PUBLIC AWARENESS

Sweden - Keeping Malmö cool

Nordic life is built for cold — bodies, homes, whole cities. But rising heat is a new, unexpected challenge changing everything.

Context

Malmö is a **modern, multicultural city** in Southern **Sweden**, overlooking the Øresund strait, as a maritime crossroads in the Baltic Sea. Connected to Denmark by the longest bridge combined with a tunnel in Europe, its cutting-edge design and growing technology sector define the new face of a city with an important industrial past. **In the late 1970s, Malmö faced a major recession** that hit its

once-strong shipbuilding and manufacturing industries hard. When the city's largest employer shut down in 1986, unemployment surged and many middle-class families left the city. By 1985, Malmö had lost around 35,000 residents. The crisis deepened through the '80s and '90s. This marked a turning point: Malmö could no longer rely on heavy industry and began **reinventing itself as a hub for**

culture, design and technology. Over the past 15 years, Malmö's leaders have carefully crafted a long-term vision to blend its medieval heritage with modern, sustainable architecture. The result is a vibrant city of minimalist design, historic charm, green spaces, and popular beaches. Urban planners from around the world now look to Malmö for inspiration on how to successfully combine tradition, innovation, and sustainability. The "Turning Torso" skyscraper by Calatrava is the symbol of Malmö's new life.

The case study of the research in Malmö was Rosengård, a low-income public housing neighborhood built between the end of '60s and the beginning of '70s in the framework of the Million programme, a large-scale public housing project, aimed to provide affordable and modern housing to the growing urban population.

The research began with the assumption that this neighborhood, home to many residents from outside Sweden, would reveal both significant vulnerabilities and strong adaptive capacities.

Stakeholders

This pilot case study brought together a diverse group of stakeholders, from civil society and academia to the private sector and non-profit organizations, to tackle the growing threat of heatwaves in urban areas. At its core, the study focused on how extreme heat impacts the city's most vulnerable residents, aiming to drive inclusive and informed solutions.

The Municipality of Malmö

Historically, the city of Malmö has focused on

preparing its infrastructure for harsh winters. However, with rising temperatures and the growing impact of urban heat islands, the city is [now turning its attention to heat vulnerability](#). The municipality is actively exploring how to integrate heat resilience into urban planning, ensuring that new buildings are designed to withstand higher temperatures and that existing structures can be adapted to meet this emerging challenge. Their goal is to embed heat considerations into the upcoming city plan, with a strong emphasis on protecting vulnerable populations.

The Public Housing Company MKB

A key local partner in the project was the public housing company, a relevant player in Sweden where **the responsibility for climate adaptation lies with property owners**. With their broad mandate and deep local presence, they were an ideal collaborator. The research protocol was co-designed with the lo-

cal partner and the Adaptation AGORA team shadowed their community officer, and went door-to-door, speaking with residents to gather firsthand insights into their perceptions and experiences.

Challenges

Nordic countries and Nordic people are used to dealing with extreme cold. Their bodies, the buildings they live in, their cities are prepared for cold. Heat in the Nordics is a recent effect of climate change that local communities were not expecting to face. A challenge to the way Nordic societies have been living so far. This is why **urban heat vulnerability**, with a focus on engaging vulnerable groups, **was the key research topic** of the Swedish pilot region. Heatwaves are more frequent and intense, with unequal impacts across neighbourhoods and citizens.

Malmö is leading the way in tackling climate adaptation, setting itself apart by actively involving its citizens in shaping the city's strategy,

including vulnerable groups to shape a heat resilient city. This approach marks a significant shift in Sweden, where urban planning has traditionally followed a top-down, engineering-driven model, relying on strong public trust in institutions rather than public participation. Malmö's commitment to citizen engagement signals a bold and refreshing change.

Heat preparedness was the key topic of [a dedicated webinar of the peer-to-peer learning series](#). The Municipality of Malmö discussed their plans and actions with the Municipality of Valencia, one of the Adaptation AGORA's followers.

Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project's four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a **structured participatory pathway**:

an inception workshop to spark dialogue and map key stakeholders; focus groups to explore local vulnerabilities and co-design ideas; and a final co-creation workshop to refine solutions and chart implementation strategies. The **emphasis was on soft adaptation measures**, non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure.

In Malmö, **112 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, academia, and business were identified and engaged when kicking-off the inception workshop. This approach bridged community insights with policymaking, laying the foundation for long-term impact.

2. Inception workshop

September 2023: The project launched its first pilot activity in Malmö, Sweden, in September 2023 with a dynamic workshop bringing together stakeholders from diverse backgrounds. The focus: how to adapt to rising heatwaves, and who's most at risk. After a brief intro from the Stockholm Environment Institute on Adaptation AGORA and the EU Mission on Adaptation, participants split into groups to explore the meaning of climate vulnerability. Discussions zoomed in on the social and physical factors that shape how different communities experience extreme heat. Using academic research on at-risk groups, participants debated who is most vulnerable and why. Key themes included the need for intersectional approaches, systems thinking, and inclusive urban planning. This inception workshop laid the groundwork for the next phases.

3. Focus groups

Summer 2024: In Malmö, the standard path of focus groups was coupled with interviews

with residents living in the Rosengård neighbourhood to understand lived experiences of heatwaves. The interviews involved around 100 residents, collecting their views and perceptions on heat vulnerability. The focus groups involved **three key segments of Malmö's society: young people, workers, and multicultural communities**. In these sessions, participants didn't just share their perspectives, they actively shaped the path forward. Together, they assessed the most promising soft climate adaptation solutions and explored the most effective ways to engage their communities in putting those ideas into action. The goal: ensure solutions are not only smart but also practical, inclusive, and rooted in everyday realities.

4. Co-creation workshop

The end of 2024 marked an important milestone for Malmö, where the municipality published a politically backed report based on Adaptation AGORA project findings, **“Extremvärme i Malmö: Vem drabbas och hur kan vi lindra effekterna?”** (Extreme Heat in Malmö: Who is Affected and How Can We Mitigate the Effects?). The co-authored report is available only in Swedish and explores urban heat vulnerability. The report positions Malmö as a great example, inspiring other cities to follow suit. In **January 2025**, SEI HQ and the City of Malmö hosted a vibrant **co-creation workshop focused on urban heat resilience**, collecting the inputs from the previous phases of the engagement path and bringing outcomes to future initiatives. **Nearly 40 participants** from across city departments came together to break silos and confront the growing risks of heatwaves. The City of Malmö used the event to launch a new working group dedicated to integrating heat mitigation into urban planning. Presentations from local experts and external voices explored key questions: Who is most affected by heat stress? What have we learned through Adaptation AGORA? How can cities plan for a hotter future?

An interactive session followed, where participants co-developed practical solutions and assigned responsibilities. The results focused on four key areas:

- 1. Nature-based solutions** – Expand and care for green spaces to cool the city equitably.
- 2. Indoor design strategies** – Boost thermal comfort with shading, insulation, and new cooling tech.
- 3. Knowledge exchange** – Learn from other cities and build capacity across departments.
- 4. Targeted communication** – Reach the most vulnerable with clear, accessible heat-risk info.

Results

What We Learned from listening: Heat, Trust, and Everyday Resilience

In Malmö’s Rosengård, statistics might label the community as vulnerable, but reality is more complex. Residents cherish their neighborhood, enjoy the green spaces, and don’t always see heat as a major concern, unless it’s sweltering indoors. This revealed a key insight: **vulnerability is not just data, it’s lived experience**, and citizen engagement is essential to uncovering it.

Across all four Adaptation AGORA pilot regions, different groups brought different needs and perspectives:

- **Youth** in Malmö preferred **reliable, decentralized communication** (like transit displays or radio alerts) over participatory methods, reflecting strong trust in public institutions.
- **Workers** favored **practical, low-effort for-**

mats, like in-situ sessions at workplaces or public alerts, highlighting a need for time-efficient, low-threshold engagement.

- **Multicultural communities** valued **culturally rooted formats**, such as storytelling, food, or art, making engagement feel personal and relatable.

- **Outdoor workers** leaned toward **passive tools like local alert systems** but remained skeptical of citizen-led initiatives, trusting formal institutions to lead in emergencies.

Educational approaches also mattered: **school-based, intergenerational learning and hands-on environmental education**, especially when embedded in everyday spaces, were seen as both effective and accessible.

One common thread? **High institutional trust** shaped how people saw their role in climate adaptation. Many preferred that public authorities take the lead, as educators, pro-

tectors, and planners. Ultimately, the project experience confirmed **that effective climate engagement isn’t one-size-fits-all**. It must be **context-aware, culturally resonant, and grounded in people’s daily lives**.

Building on the strong foundation laid by Adaptation AGORA, the legacy of community-driven climate resilience lives on through the new HeatSafe project. Funded by Formas, HeatSafe brings together SEI HQ, the City of Malmö, Linköping University, and Imagine Adaptation (led by BC3) to deepen research and develop advanced decision-support tools, ensuring Malmö stays prepared and protected as heat risks rise. Thanks to the legacy of Adaptation AGORA, Malmö is not just staying cool in the face of rising temperatures, it’s staying cool as a modern, forward-thinking city, ready and equipped to tackle new climate challenges with confidence and innovation.

Sweden's pathway

Malmö

Keeping the City Cool

watch the video

Malmö is a modern multicultural city that has reinvented itself from an industrial hub into a center of design, technology, and sustainability. Internationally recognized for integrating innovation, tradition, and green living, its landscape blends medieval heritage with contemporary architecture, symbolized by Calatrava's Turning Torso. The city-specific pathway focused on Rosengård, a low-income public housing neighborhood, revealing both vulnerabilities and strong adaptive capacities.

LOCAL IMPACTS

VULNERABILITIES

- Historic **prioritization of winter-proof infrastructure**
- Unprepared **vulnerable groups of citizens**, such as elderly or outdoor workers

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

The case study brought together a diverse group of **112 STAKEHOLDERS** from civil society and academia to the private sector and non-profit organizations. **Among those, two were the key partners.**

Municipality

Public Housing Company MKB

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

INCEPTION WORKSHOP

FOCUS GROUPS & INTERVIEWS

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

September 2023

Summer 2024

January 2025

RESULTS

Spain - Urban and Rural Adaptation

From villages to cities, every voice matters in climate adaptation. In Aragón, climate challenges and solutions from both dimensions bridge countryside and urban settlements, reflecting the full diversity of our society.

Context

The region of Aragón is an autonomous community in northeastern Spain, characterized by a remarkable **variety of landscapes**, from the Pyrenean mountains and alpine valleys with glaciers, to rolling hills, deep canyons, the Ebro River basin, and vast steppe areas. It is also renowned for its **rich historical and ar-**

chitectural heritage, especially the **Mudéjar style**, which blends Islamic and Christian elements.

The regional capital is Zaragoza, the most populous city in Aragón, is a key hub for transportation, commerce, and logistics. The city

combines history and modernity: its compact, heritage-rich centre is home to numerous landmarks, while the surrounding districts have seen significant growth, especially in logistics and residential development. Zaragoza continues to expand with strong public services and a focus on **sustainable urban planning**, including **green infrastructure** and **eco-friendly neighbourhoods**.

Zaragoza has a **semi-arid climate** with Mediterranean influences. Summers are hot and dry, often exceeding 35°C, while winters are relatively mild. In recent years, however, the city has faced **significant climate challenges**, which have driven it to take proactive measures. Zaragoza is now recognized as a **leading city in climate adaptation**, with for example a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan and implementing green infrastructure and urban renaturalization.

Stakeholders

Government of Aragón

The Government of Aragón is striving to **keep pace with scientific knowledge**, which often moves faster than the implementation of policies and solutions across such a large and diverse region. While European funding provides crucial support, the government sometimes faces challenges related to limited human resources. A key point of convergence with the Adaptation AGORA project is the shared emphasis on **citizen participation**, which allows decision-makers to explore scenarios that would otherwise be difficult to identify. Another essential pillar for the government is **combating misinformation**.

Aragón is implementing several policy strategies, including the **Aragón Climate Change Strategy**, a living document that evolves alongside the region's economic and social development. The government is also advancing **nature-based solutions** and **spatial renaturalization initiatives**. A flagship initiative is the **Aragón Climate Week**, a series of events in collaboration with institutions, associations, and private partners. This week-long program spans the region, providing **information, tools, and practical actions to support adaptation and mitigation efforts** for the entire Aragonese society.

Zaragoza City Council

The primary goal of Zaragoza is clear and ambitious: to become a resilient and **climate-neutral city by 2030**. The city is addressing climate change through a broad range of actions, fully aligned with European Union and national policies. Zaragoza is implementing measures within its **adaptation plan**, as well

as initiatives linked to the mission of “**smart and climate-neutral cities,**” of which it is an active member.

The connection with the Adaptation AGORA project lies primarily in **citizen participation:** listening to residents’ voices, understanding their needs, and involving them in decision-making. Equally important is ensuring that these decisions are **communicated effectively,** minimizing the risk of **misinformation or misunderstanding.**

University of Zaragoza

The academic world in Zaragoza represented a stakeholder genuinely open to dialogue, sharing a mindset aligned with the project’s approach. The University of Zaragoza strives to remain **engaged with society** rather than isolating itself within a bubble of publications and research. It aims to serve as an example

of **good governance, fostering proactive attitudes and a mindset open to change.** Research must go **hand in hand with citizens** and their needs, to truly **understand the gaps and challenges society faces** at any given moment. Only by doing so can research become genuinely useful, helping to **address societal problems and tackle global challenges** effectively.

Civil Society

From the perspective of social innovators, the key priority is to **place people at the centre of decision-making processes.** Achieving this goes beyond simply following a participatory approach, it requires ensuring that **all citizen profiles** are considered. **Inclusion is a fundamental pillar** of any process aimed at developing solutions that truly serve the city, society, and the residents who live within it. Citizens must become **active agents of change,** enabling them to see their ideas and solutions materialize in ways that are well-suited to their social and geographical environments.

Challenges

The Aragón region, located in northeastern Spain, is particularly vulnerable to **water scarcity, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation** due to its semi-arid conditions and geographic diversity stretching from the Pyrenees to the Ebro Valley. In recent years, the region has faced **rising temperatures, prolonged droughts, and increasingly frequent wildfires.** Projections point to more intense heatwaves and a **growing risk of desertification,** especially in lowland agricultural areas where crop yields and livestock production, such as pig farming, already suffer from heat stress and high irrigation demands.

Aragón’s main vulnerabilities stem from its heavy reliance on water-intensive agriculture, combined with demographic challenges such as **rural depopulation and ageing communities in isolated areas.** These dynamics reduce the adaptive capacity of local economies and **exacerbate social inequalities.** Low-income and elderly populations, in both rural and urban contexts, are especially exposed, often lacking access to sufficient cooling systems, resilient infrastructure, or the financial means to implement adaptation measures. Despite a robust climate strategy aligned with

national and EU frameworks, Aragón continues to face significant hurdles in translating plans into local action. More effective coordination, funding, and regulatory support are urgently needed.

Urban centres like Zaragoza, where most of the pilot activities took place, face intensified **urban heat island effects** and heightened **flood risks from extreme rainfall.** With annual precipitation both scarce and unevenly distributed, the city is **increasingly vulnerable to droughts and heatwaves.** The heat island effect is particularly acute in older, densely built areas, while social inequalities, such as the lack of green spaces in lower-income neighbourhoods, further exacerbate these challenges.

Energy poverty remains also a pressing challenge in cities like Zaragoza, affecting vulnerable communities and limiting access to essential energy services. This topic was addressed in a [dedicated webinar of the peer-to-peer learning series](#), together with the Municipality of Almada (Portugal) and Valencia (Spain), two followers of the Adaptation AGORA project and the city of Barcelona.

Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project's four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a **structured participatory pathway**: an inception workshop to map key stakeholders, engage different target audiences and decision-makers, and identify local barriers and vulnerabilities; followed by focus groups with specific populations to better understand their concerns and unique perspectives; and culminating in a final co-creation workshop aimed at developing actionable proposals and contributions to adaptation measures. The **emphasis was on soft adaptation measures**, non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure.

Across the broader Aragón region, **93 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, health infrastructure, and business sectors were identified and actively engaged during the inception workshop. This approach effectively bridged community insights with policymaking, laying the groundwork for robust networks and long-term impact.

2. Inception workshop

September 2023: One of the core pillars of the Adaptation AGORA project is **inclusion**. To better understand both the adaptive capacity and the adaptation gap in Aragón, **two inception workshops** were organised: one in **Valderrobres**, the main town in the **rural area of Matarraña** and another in **Zaragoza**, where most pilot activities were concentrated. These workshops provided an initial partici-

patory diagnosis of the region's exposure to climate change, **bridging perspectives from both rural and urban contexts**.

In Zaragoza, participants identified **desertification, water scarcity, extreme temperatures, and the wider impacts of climate change on health and social inequalities** as the most pressing risks. Through participatory methods such as impact mapping and topic prioritisation, key entry points for co-creation emerged, particularly around **social inequality and water-related vulnerabilities**.

Discussions highlighted **urban-rural disparities**, ageing populations, and the concentration of vulnerable communities as central challenges. In Zaragoza, participants also emphasised the need to tackle broader socio-spatial injustices alongside climate risks.

The workshops concluded with a shared recognition that critical issues such as **social inequality, public health, and water poverty** must serve as priority areas for action. These themes were later further explored through citizen and stakeholder co-creation within the Adaptation AGORA focus groups.

3. Focus groups

In Zaragoza, as in the other pilot regions, the **Summer 2024** focus groups engaged specific target groups: **young people, workers, multicultural communities, and a group of elderly residents from the rural area of Matarraña**. In the rural area, rather than following a rigid co-creation methodology, the session created open conversational spaces where participants could share personal stories, such as memories of past heatwaves.

In Zaragoza, the focus group's proposals centred on the **social dimensions of adaptation**, particularly inequality and the limited responsiveness of institutions. Participants underlined the **importance of education** not only as a tool to raise awareness but also as a way to strengthen critical thinking. They highlighted that education could play a decisive role in countering misinformation, fostering **informed engagement**, and promoting both social inclusion and active participation in climate action.

4. Co-creation workshop

At the **beginning of 2025**, in Zaragoza, the final co-creation workshop was built directly on the local concerns, vulnerabilities, and proposals co-developed by citizens, using the focus groups outcomes as a basis. During the focus groups, themes such as **urban heat, social inequality, rural-urban disconnection, and working conditions were highlighted**. The need for public infrastructure that supports resilience (e.g., **climate shelters**), for improving the working conditions during heatwaves, and for inclusive public awareness strategies, were part of the discussions. These insights were not only taken forward as topics during the final co-creation workshop but also helped shape its structure, which was devised

to **refine, prioritise, and further co-create solutions** around these **citizen-identified needs**. There, participants engaged in exercises to refine collaboratively and prioritise soft adaptation solutions initially identified during the earlier focus groups.

Results

Adaptation to climate change is not only about technical solutions but about inclusion, fairness, and listening to communities

The co-creation sessions in Zaragoza brought forward a set of soft adaptation solutions that link **climate resilience with social inclusion**. Participants emphasised that adaptation must not only respond to environmental risks but also address inequalities, depopulation, and gaps in governance. Across the groups, there was a clear preference for community-led, low-cost initiatives that **foster partici-**

pation, trust, and fairness, rather than purely technological approaches.

Youth highlighted the vulnerability of precarious and outdoor workers to extreme heat and prioritised improvements in working conditions. They also advocated for the creation of **climate shelters as safe and accessible cooling spaces** during heatwaves, and for **policies that strengthen urban-rural connections**, including ones to support young people in reconnecting with smaller villages, where climate pressures might be lower and more sustainable lifestyles could be encouraged. Young people called for **climate education** in schools and more inclusive communication strategies to counter misinformation with constructive, action-oriented narratives.

Workers echoed concerns about **heat stress** and like youth, they identified **climate shelters and cooling infrastructure** (shaded areas, hydration points) as urgent priorities.

Multicultural communities proposed solu-

tions that integrate **environmental measures with social equity**. This included **reforestation**, the **creation of energy communities to make renewable energy more inclusive**, and **clearer renewable energy policies** accessible to marginalised groups. Importantly, they emphasised **inclusive and multilingual communication** to reach linguistically diverse communities and advocated for gender-sensitive climate migration policies.

Elderly participants in rural Matarraña contributed practical knowledge from past experiences, including coping strategies for heatwaves, while raising concerns about **riverbed maintenance to reduce flooding risks** and about the impacts of prolonged droughts.

These insights highlight how citizens in Zaragoza view adaptation as inseparable from **inclusion, fairness, and everyday community life, making social justice the foundation of resilience**.

Spain's pathway

Aragón region

Urban and Rural Adaptation

watch the video

The region of Aragón is an autonomous community in northeastern Spain, characterized by a remarkable variety of landscapes and renowned for its rich historical and architectural heritage. The regional capital is Zaragoza, the most populous city in Aragón, is a key hub for transportation, commerce, and logistics. Zaragoza has a semi-arid climate with Mediterranean influences. In recent years, however, the city has faced significant climate challenges, which have driven it to take proactive measures.

LOCAL IMPACTS

VULNERABILITIES

- Semi-arid climate rises vulnerability for **water scarcity, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation, and desertification**
- Rural depopulation and **ageing communities in isolated areas**
- **Energy poverty** limiting access to essential energy services

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

STAKEHOLDERS

who have been involved belonged to **4 key groups**.

Government of Aragón Zaragoza City Council University of Zaragoza Civil Society

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

RESULTS

Germany - Go where citizens are

Citizen engagement is a challenging journey. But it becomes truly meaningful when we step into people’s spaces, listen to their voices, and meet them where they are, rather than expecting them to come to us.

Context

Dresden, the capital of Saxony in eastern Germany, is set along the banks of the Elbe River and its valley, once recognized as a UNESCO World Heritage Site. Known as the “Florence on the Elbe”, the city is celebrated for its **baroque architecture, rich cultural legacy, and**

abundant green spaces. Dresden’s history is marked by **resilience as much as by beauty.** Since 1989, like many major urban centers in Saxony, the city has experienced steady population decline due to migration to the former West Germany. Yet demographic shifts

tell only part of its story. Over the centuries, Dresden endured **repeated devastation:** a great fire in 1491, Prussian bombings in 1760, the violent suppression of the 1849 constitutional protests, and most tragically, the Allied air raids of 1945, which left much of the **city in ruins.**

The urban fabric today reflects both continuity and renewal. The **Altstadt** (Old Town), with its Renaissance and baroque landmarks, has seen many of **its iconic buildings meticulously reconstructed** to their former grandeur after wartime destruction. Across the river, the **Neustadt** (New Town) serves as both a **residential and governmental hub,** renowned for its vibrant cultural scene, contemporary art, and lively nightlife, an alternative and creative counterbalance to the historic center.

Dresden is also one of **Germany’s greenest cities:** over **60% of its territory** is covered by forests, parks, and open spaces. This commitment to preserving the natural environment is reflected in the **city’s planning and development strategies.** At the same time, Dresden’s context, shaped by **ageing infrastructure, demographic challenges, and urban growth,** has fostered a pragmatic, institutionally focused approach to **climate adaptation and sustainable development.**

Stakeholders

The stakeholders involved in this pilot case study were diverse, ranging from institutions in the **health sector to private companies, associations, and representatives of the municipal administration.** The process of mapping stakeholders in each pilot region not only provided an overview of relevant actors

but also created entry points to reach specific target groups and citizens. In many cases, stakeholders acted as bridges, enabling more direct and active engagement with the public.

Through this collaboration, the project gained valuable know-how and a deeper understanding of the challenges involved in reaching target populations. One key lesson was that it is often more effective to go where citizens are, in their own spaces and contexts, rather than simply inviting them to come to the project.

The city of Dresden

Another key stakeholder in the Dresden pilot case was the **municipality** itself. In recent years, the city has been experiencing a range of climate change impacts, including **heatwaves, rising temperatures, and flooding.** One of the main priorities for the administration has been addressing extreme heat, which

grows more intense with each passing year. Since 2017, an interdisciplinary team of researchers and operational partners has been working on how urban neighborhoods and buildings can **better adapt to summer heat**. From this effort, the [HeatResilientCity project](#) was launched: a transdisciplinary initiative aimed at exploring how **densely populated districts**, such as Dresden-Gorbitz, and their residents can be **protected from extreme heat**.

Following the **record-breaking temperatures of July 2023**, the project also produced a “[Heat Handbook](#)” for professionals in the health, social, educational, and housing sectors. The handbook provides practical **guidance on preventing and managing the impacts of heatwaves**, with a strong focus on the Gorbitz district. It includes information on Dresden’s urban climate, introduces the **health consequences of extreme heat**, and highlights the specific factors that contribute to **heat stress** in the neighborhood.

Building on these efforts, the city is also developing a comprehensive [Heat Protection Plan](#) to **safeguard public health against increasingly frequent and intense heatwaves**. Across all these actions, Dresden’s administration places strong emphasis on citizen engagement, recognizing that effective adaptation requires the **active involvement of residents**. The collaboration with the project has been instrumental in strengthening the city’s **know-how on how to meaningfully involve its citizens in co-developing climate adaptation solutions**.

The Municipal Hospital

The participation of **Dresden’s municipal hospital** as one of the city’s key stakeholders proved particularly important, as it shed light on the complex relationship between **health**

care and climate change. This relationship is bidirectional, and it was explored in depth thanks to the involvement of healthcare professionals in the project’s activities. For example, nurses experience the direct impact of **extreme heat and heatwaves** in their daily work, yet they can also play an active role in advancing **adaptation measures within the hospital**. These measures not only enable them to **work under better conditions** but also ensure that patients, who often feel the effects of climate change most acutely, either by developing new conditions or by aggravating pre-existing ones, **receive appropriate care** in a safe and livable environment.

More broadly, the health sector in Germany is responsible for around **5% of national greenhouse gas emissions**. For this reason, the municipal hospital is actively pursuing emission reduction strategies while also working to develop **adaptation solutions**, efforts that have been further strengthened through its participation in and collaboration with Adaptation AGORA.

Private Sector - Sandstorm

The city of Dresden is already implementing a variety of **digital tools** and online platforms to meet the needs of residents who are comfortable engaging through these channels, as well as to address a wide range of needs related to city resources that are not widely known. A clear example is the [city’s thematic map](#), available on the municipal website, which highlights the locations of **free drinking water in Dresden**.

The city’s commitment to exploring digital tools as solutions to specific needs is already evident. One of the stakeholders attending the co-creation workshop was **Sandstorm**, a digital agency that combines technology, design, and sustainability to deliver bespoke digital solutions. With a strong focus on sustainable practices, Sandstorm applies sustainable coding, developing efficient, low-resource software.

Sandstorm is the agency behind **Cleema**, a free mobile app for Android and iOS designed **to promote sustainable behaviour** in everyday life, with a particular focus on Dresden. Its main goal is to **engage and inform citizens on environmental issues**, encouraging participation in local initiatives and raising climate awareness. The app uses gamification elements, such as challenges and quizzes, to inspire daily action.

This philosophy mirrors the Adaptation AGORA project’s approach in developing the **AGORA Quiz app**, also available for [Android](#) and [iOS](#). Through an engaging, game-based format, the app invites citizens to explore the **science of climate change**, understand how it is communicated and sometimes distorted through disinformation, and learn about the core principles and practical measures of both adaptation and mitigation.

Non-profit Associations

The engagement with local non-profit associations proved equally valuable. A particularly active collaboration was established with [Internationale Gärten Dresden](#), a volunteer-driven **non-profit association** dedicated to community gardening, integration, education, and intercultural exchange. Much like Adaptation AGORA, the association strives **to give a voice to groups within society that are often unheard**.

Its main goal is to create a community garden in Dresden where people from different countries can grow fruit and vegetables on equal terms, while getting to know each other and exchanging ideas. The International Gardens Dresden provides a space for **personal initiative, self-organization, and the sharing of knowledge**.

At the heart of the initiative lies the strengthening of everyday democratic culture and, consequently, civil society. Values such as in-

clusion, community participation, and network-building are closely aligned with the objectives of the project. The collaboration with the association offered practical and meaningful insights into citizen engagement.

Challenges

Dresden has an **oceanic climate with continental influences**, characterized by warm summers and relatively cold winters. In recent years, however, the city has become increasingly exposed to **rising temperatures**, drier summers, wetter winters, and **more frequent extreme weather events**. Vulnerability is further shaped by **rapid urbanisation, population growth, and socio-demographic dynamics** such as an ageing population. Densely built-up areas are particularly affected by the **urban heat island effect**, which amplifies **overheating, raises public health risks, and increases energy demand**.

The city's location along the Elbe River and its tributaries also makes it highly susceptible

to **flooding** during episodes of heavy rainfall, as demonstrated by the **devastating floods of 2002 and 2013**. More recently, flash floods and overloaded drainage systems have become increasingly common due to **intense precipitation and rising groundwater levels**, pushing both the Elbe and urban water infrastructure to their limits. Urban expansion and extensive soil sealing have further reduced natural water retention, underlining the **urgent need for green infrastructure and decentralised rainwater management**.

At the same time, Dresden is facing **more frequent and intense storms and prolonged heatwaves**, all linked to ongoing climate change. These trends present significant **adaptation challenges across infrastructure, governance, and the economy**. Energy systems, transport networks, and tourism infrastructure remain highly vulnerable to climate-induced disruptions.

In response, the city has launched several adaptation initiatives, including the "**Schwammstadt Project**" (Sponge City Project), which adopts the **sponge city approach to enhance resilience**. The concept **reimagines the**

urban landscape as a resilient ecosystem designed to naturally absorb, store, filter, and reuse rainwater, reducing surface runoff and flood risks while recharging groundwater and improving the local microclimate.

Despite these efforts, progress remains uneven. Fragmented governance structures, outdated building codes, and limited financial resources continue to slow the pace of adaptation.

Participatory pathway

1. General structure

The project's four pilot areas served as testing grounds for inclusive, community-led climate adaptation. Starting in 2023, each area followed a structured participatory pathway: an inception workshop to map key stakeholders, engage different target audiences and decision-makers, and identify local barriers and vulnerabilities; followed by focus groups with specific populations to better understand their concerns and unique perspectives; and culminating in a final co-creation workshop aimed at developing actionable proposals and contributions to adaptation measures. The **emphasis was on soft adaptation measures**, non-structural, low-cost actions like public education and early warning systems, that address real community needs without heavy infrastructure.

In Dresden, **256 stakeholders** from public institutions, civil society, health infrastructure, and business sectors were identified and actively engaged during the inception workshop. This approach effectively bridged community

insights with policymaking, laying the groundwork for robust networks and long-term impact.

The activities successfully involved key societal groups, including **youth actively engaged in climate action, working populations in the health sector, multicultural communities, people with disabilities and seniors**. Particular attention was given to ensuring broad representation across public authorities, local communities, civil society organizations, academia and research institutions, the private sector, and the media.

2. Inception workshop

September 2023: The inception workshop in Dresden explored key climate-related risks, with **heatwaves and heavy rainfalls and floods** considered as the primary hazards of concern. Participants discussed how these risks affect the urban environment, including impacts on infrastructure, housing, and individual well-being. While both hazards were acknowledged, heatwaves emerged as a particularly pressing issue due to their increasingly frequent and prolonged occurrence in recent years. A central focus of the workshop was on how **social vulnerability intersects with climate risks**. Participants reflected on the fact that adaptation needs and capacities vary significantly across population groups. For example, senior residents and people with chronic illnesses or disabilities were seen as particularly at risk, especially when living in **poorly adapted housing** or alone, with limited access to information or support. Discussions also addressed **economic vulnerability**, such as limited access to air conditioning or other coping resources. From an inclusion and capacity perspective, the workshop highlighted several **barriers to adaptation**. These included limited public awareness, lack of institutional coordination, and **insufficient representation of vulnerable communities** in climate planning processes. At the same time, existing civil society initiatives, community-based networks, and the city's infrastructure for public engagement were mentioned as potential assets for supporting local adaptation responses.

3. Focus groups

The co-creation of **soft climate adaptation solutions** was carried out through a series of focus groups across the four pilot regions. Across all pilots, particular attention was gi-

ven to **accessibility and inclusivity**, including selecting convenient locations, scheduling sessions outside typical working hours, and adapting facilitation strategies to the needs of specific target groups. Each session began with a brief preparatory phase designed to establish a shared understanding of the session's objectives and to create a welcoming, comfortable environment for participants.

Summer 2024: In Dresden the first focus group involved **youth actively engaged in climate action**. Two additional focus groups engaged **professional caregivers** working in a public hospital. Another group consisted of participants from **multicultural communities**, who proposed several soft adaptation measures inspired by **traditional knowledge** from their countries of origin and adapted to the local context.

In Dresden, the co-creation process also extended to **vulnerable populations**, in addition to the target groups common across the other pilot regions. This was addressed through two separate focus groups: one with **seniors**, and another with **people with disabilities and chronic illnesses**. The latter group developed a set of measures **prioritizing inclusive and accessible approaches to climate resilience**, ensuring that adaptation strategies respond to the specific needs of all community members.

Vulnerabilities and [the climate-health nexus](#) were the focus of a dedicated webinar of the [peer-to-peer learning series](#). The city of Dresden shared experiences and views with Grenoble and Barcelona.

4. Co-creation workshop

At the beginning of 2025 the final co-creation workshops were organised with the common purpose all over the four pilot regions to work on **citizen-generated ideas** from previous phases, evaluate their **feasibility and relevance**, and identify meaningful strategies for their implementation through **inclusive engagement methods**. In Dresden, thematic sub-workshops were organised around four adaptation topics:

1. **Effective Climate Communication**
2. **Participatory City Design** (including Digital tools)
3. **Educational initiatives in schools**
4. **Financing climate adaptation**

These formed the basis for collaborative refinement, allowing participants to explore how the ideas emerging from the previous focus groups could be translated into concrete, actionable measures at the local level.

Results

Voicing the voiceless: awareness, citizen engagement and building a network

During the last co-creation workshop participants consolidated proposals from all focus groups into a few key directions: shifting from fear-based to inclusive messaging, enhancing digital participatory tools with features like mapping shaded areas and water points, promoting school-based awareness campaigns with hands-on learning and intergenerational exchange, and identifying funding strategies that integrate adaptation into existing city budgets.

Different groups brought different needs and perspectives during focus groups meetings:

- **Youth** in Dresden proposed a **school-based awareness campaign on climate adaptation**,

combining hands-on climate education with community-led action groups. They emphasized that engagement should be enjoyable, accessible, and voluntary to be effective.

- **Professional caregivers** highlighted the dual challenge of safeguarding their own wellbeing while ensuring patient care. Proposed measures included **heat-triggered protocols, more flexible work schedules, and adaptable work clothing systems**, addressing both health protection and care standards.

- **Multicultural communities** focused on raising awareness and building solidarity around visible, everyday adaptation practices. They suggested soft adaptation measures inspired by **traditional knowledge** from their countries of origin, such as **passive cooling techniques** like using stored rainwater to water rooftops during heat events.

- **Vulnerable populations**, seniors and people with disabilities and chronic illnesses, developed measures reflecting their specific needs, particularly regarding extreme heat. They showed interest in accessible engagement formats, including surveys and online platforms, and expressed willingness to act as public representatives for campaigns **promoting inclusive climate adaptation**. Participants stressed the importance of inclusive formats, such as audio descriptions and simplified language, to ensure information reaches all community members.

Germany's pathway

Dresden

Go where Citizens are

watch the video

Dresden, the capital of Saxony along the Elbe River, is known for its baroque architecture, cultural heritage, and extensive green spaces. Its history blends beauty and resilience, marked by fires, bombings, and major reconstruction after 1945. Today, the Altstadt (Old Town) reflects restored historic grandeur, while the Neustadt (New Town) offers a vibrant cultural and residential scene. In this context, the city has embraced a pragmatic, institution-driven approach to sustainability and climate adaptation.

LOCAL IMPACTS

- Rising temperatures
- Intense precipitation
- Rising groundwater level

VULNERABILITIES

- **60% of territory covered in green spaces** and the city is committed to preserve it
- Location along the **Elbe river**
- **Population growth & rapid urbanization**
- **Ageing population & infrastructures**

RISKS AND CHALLENGES

- Flash floods
- Overloaded drainage systems
- Urban heat island effect
- Increased energy demand

STAKEHOLDERS were mapped across each city region, reaching citizens in their own spaces and contexts. **Those involved belonged to 4 key groups.**

PARTICIPATORY PATHWAY

RESULTS

Tuscan-Emilian Apennines in northern Italy, from Copernicus Sentinel-2 ©ESA

The “Voices” Gallery

Voices

Meet the people behind the process, from the project team members to local stakeholders, policymakers, institutions, NGOs, academics, and everyday citizens. Each voice offers a unique perspective, sharing their experiences, ideas, and contributions to shaping place-based adaptation journeys. Together, they bring to life the rich, collective effort driving local resilience across Europe.

Scan the QR code to dive into the gallery.

Hear firsthand stories from the people who contributed to shaping the project and **browse by media type or location** to **explore different perspectives.**

ERS-2 radar view of Strait of Messina, Italy ©ESA

Glossary

Discover the language of climate adaptation. This glossary offers clear, accessible definitions of key terms to help you navigate the complex world of climate adaptation, from policies and practices to people and processes. Whether you're a newcomer or a seasoned expert, these terms will support deeper understanding and more informed action.

The language of Climate Adaptation

Below are some of the key words shaping the **Voices of Climate Adaptation glossary**. Click [here](#) to explore and learn more.

Adaptation

Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. Various types of adaptation can be distinguished, including anticipatory and reactive adaptation, private and public adaptation, and autonomous and planned adaptation

Capacity Building

The process by which individuals or organizations obtain, improve, or retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, or other resources to do their work competently

Climate change disinformation

Climate disinformation is the intentional dissemination of false information related to climate change and climate action. It can take many forms, from hard denial and conspiracy theories to softer, more insidious disinformation that seeks to muddy the waters by claiming that climate change is not man-made or as bad as scientists are saying and therefore requires no urgent action.

Citizen Engagement

Refers to the active participation of individuals and communities in governance processes, encompassing decision-making, implementation, and monitoring

Co-creation

Collaboratively creating outputs like tools or policy recommendations. A process that can add value and increase innovative potential through intentional experience design

Public Awareness

A process that seeks to inform and educate people about a topic or issue with the intention of influencing their attitudes, behaviours and beliefs towards the achievement of a defined purpose or goal.

www.voicesofclimateadaptation.dataclime.com